

Running head: Level Up to HLM

Level Up to HLM: A Way to Handle Multilevel Data

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Abstract

This paper firstly provides a conceptual explanation of Hierarchical Linear Modeling. It provides rationale for its development, its applications as well as some of its limitations. It also delves briefly into the topic's relatively short history. It is the hope of the author that this paper will motivate the reader to learn more about the method and consider its use when appropriate in their practice. Secondly it provides a Monte Carlo Simulation made by the Author to determine how multilevel data influences the true type I error rate of one sample t-tests under a range of specific conditions. It is work the author believes is novel and could very well be built upon by future students. Lastly the author also hopes this research will help raise awareness of how multilevel data can result in increased type I error in their work and how HLM is one means of dealing with such an issue.

Level Up to HLM: A Way to Handle Multilevel Data

Part I: A Detailed Introduction to the Subject

For many years statisticians had often been doing things wrong with their ordinary least squares regression (OLS) when it came to hierarchical data. For they had overlooked how presumably independent members of a sample could actually have covariance in groups within that sample, thus they were violating the assumption of independent sampling also known as independence of sampling errors (Woltman, H., Feldstain, A., MacKay, J. C., & Rocchi, M. 2012), resulting in an increased risk of committing type I error. Handling the data in this way was called disaggregation and was one of two past ways of dealing with hierarchical groups in data. The other way was called aggregation, in which the variables are moved to the higher levels of hierarchy thus you are dealing with means of the lower levels of data as an outcome as opposed to dealing with an outcome at the lowest level. Not only does this potentially force you to change your research question, but you also can lose a lot of that variability in your lower level data potentially leading you to mischaracterize the relationship between outcome and predictor variables.

To further illustrate matters, I have used excel to make up data with three groups. For some fun, let's say that these are 9 chess players, and we are comparing amount of tournaments played to amount of money earned and they just so happen to enter in tournaments in teams of 3, so that they can share their winnings with one another. By disaggregation and acting as if there are no teams or aggregating and averaging the values within the teams, we find in either case, a negative trend (see appendix 6 figure 1). However, if we are able to somehow take into account the individual values as well as the groups we would find a positive association

between tournaments played and money earned (Appendix 6 see figure 2). My contrived contextual explanation for this contrived data is that teams with less experience tended to play in tournaments with less experienced players, but teams with players with more experienced players might get too confident and play in tournaments that they are not ready for. Still within each team individual experience is positively correlated with winnings. See appendix 7 for actual values of the made up data for this example.

Then in the early 1980s the technique known as Hierarchical Linear Modeling (HLM) was born. The statistical method also goes by many other names such as Multilevel Modeling and mixed effects and several other names. This may be partially due to the number of disciplines that make use of it. (Garson, 2013, p. 4) Still, regardless of what you call it, hierarchical linear modeling can be thought of as a modified version of OLS meant to take into account covariance of data due to hierarchical (nested) groups within a sample of data. You simply start with the highest level of predictor variables and create a number of regression lines that produce the intercepts and coefficients of the next highest level of data as outcome variables with the process repeating with those terms and continuing until you reach your lowest level where you find the regression line that gives you your outcome variable (see appendices 2 and 3). Of course there is the caveat that at each level your predictor variables must be centered; in other words the mean of each level is subtracted from each level's values causing the y intercept at each level to be equal to the lower level's mean. Oddly enough there are two ways to go about centering. In Group mean centering a value's group mean is subtracted from that value whereas in grand mean centering, the overall mean for that level is used. Using either method has an influence on the resulting coefficient estimates, so one should try to remember which one is being used. (Stevens, 2007, pp. 341-342) Regardless, it is usually the grand mean centering

that is performed. (Garson, 2013, p. 38) It makes sense to be using this chain of regression lines nested into one another to account for nested groups of data.

HLM is a very useful tool having numerous applications as well some drawbacks. The biggest drawback is that you need a lot of data to obtain adequate power to be useful in testing hypothesis. So if you use HLM when you don't need to, you will increase the chance of type two errors. To assess whether you need to perform HLM or not, you simply need to calculate the intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) which is the ratio of variance between groups of the outcome variable to the overall variance of the outcome variable. (See appendix 5 for a school based example) Thinking of Multilevel data in terms of clusters of data, the ICC can be thought of as the spread of the clusters in proportion to the spread of the overall data points (see appendix 4). ICC can be calculated using what is called the Null model which is a particular type of one-way ANOVA that uses only the dependent variable with random effects (Garson, 2013, p. 8). There will be less difference between HLM and OLS the lower the ICC is (Garson, 2013, p. 27). Still in an example, an ICC of 0.1 in which for a one-way ANOVA with 3 groups of 30 subjects the actual alpha is inflated to 0.4917, which is somewhat remarkable (Stevens, 2007, p. 323). Even if the ICC is not significant, it does not eliminate the possibility that you might need a coefficient mixed model since the ICC only deals with the dependent variable and not the independent variables. (Garson, 2013, p. 27) and a more complicated test is needed to rule out that possibility (Garson, 2013, p. 49).

Another important issue with regard to MLM is in determining causal relationships. It is that it is possible if one observes a relationship between an independent and a dependent variable that there is not some unaccounted variable that accounts for variability in the variables under investigation. To minimize such a risk one should use instead a fixed effects model which takes into account all unseen fixed effects. However there are drawbacks for fixed effects models as well including the inability to have research questions that investigate higher level variables as can be done with HLM. A Hausman test is traditionally used to choose between the two models assuming of course that the research question is appropriate for both models (Cook, "Fixed Effects vs Multilevel Models by William Cook", 2014). There are also other important assumptions such as random sampling, a normal distribution of residuals, proper handling of outliers and the avoidance of multicollinearity along with others which the reader is free to investigate. (Garson, 2013, pp. 36-40)

Multilevel Modeling can be used in a number of different ways wherever hierarchical data is apparent including hypothesis testing, making predictions and data reduction (Gelman, A. 2006). It can also be used for meta-analysis where subjects in various studies investigating the same research question are considered the first level while the studies themselves constitute a sample taken from a population of other studies and are considered a second level. Admittedly this application may not be very useful until many studies provide their raw data in addition to their reports. HLM is also useful in dealing with the dilemma of autocorrelation in repeated measures, and longitudinal analysis and what are called growth models by considering each measurement taken from the same observation as level one and the overall observations as the second level (Garson, 2013, p. 18). It's also interesting to note that just as linear regression can be extended into generalized linear models so too can multilevel models be extended via generalized

linear mixed models by way of linking functions and thus can be used with nominal or ordinal data or with data that follow a non-normal distribution such as a binomial, Poisson, negative binomial distribution (Garson, 2013, pp. 12-16). However, as with any linear regression it is best to avoid over fitting your data unless there is some field specific knowledge why such a specific nonlinear relationship would exist by nature of the field of inquiry.

HLM can also account for missing data but only at the lowest level of hierarchy and so because of this it is better to have more groups than to have more subjects in individual groups. (Woltman, H., Feldstain, A., MacKay, J. C., & Rocchi, M. 2012).

With HLM being so complicated in terms of all those regression lines, the reader may be wondering how one would go about performing this technique for their self. There are a number of applications with which can be used to perform HLM. They include SAS, R, SPSS and the specific HLM program (Gelman, A. 2006).

How do these programs achieve all the wondrous magic that is Multilevel Modeling? You might think as I had that the software simply performed OLS for each level to estimate the coefficients and intercepts for each level's regression equations. That is however not the case as appendices 2 and 3 are for an individual subject's outcome value and not the overall regression line. Instead these programs use maximum likelihood estimators (MLEs) and other complicated moves in an iterative process to eventually converge to the sought after parameters. Moreover, if the parameters do not converge under a certain number of iterations, the results

of the latest iteration are often outputted by the user's software with the warning that the parameters did not converge and that the values may be suboptimal. The literature lists a number of possible remedies to handle such a scenario, but it is not a focus of this paper (Garson, 2013, pp. 12-16).

It is probably because of all this computational complexity that Hierarchical Linear Models were developed only relatively recently. Still, ideas of working with hierarchical data go back a long way especially in the sociological field. According to the European Sociological Survey Education Net, contextual analysis in the 1940s America was the beginning of the road to modern, Multilevel Modeling. Over the decades that followed, more conceptual progress was made and then in the 1970s there came about the first two-stage multiple regression design meant for use in research related to education settings. Finally in the 1980s, the first Hierarchical Linear Modeling software was developed, one by a group in Chicago and called HLM and another by a group in London called LMwin (ESS EDuNet, "A short history of multilevel analysis", 2013).

To wrap up this section, Hierarchical Linear Modeling is a very useful statistical technique for dealing with data having hierarchical structure. It is relatively easy to understand its conceptual framework of interconnected regression lines, although it is very complex computationally with regard to those regression lines are estimated. It is one of the reasons why the development of HLM has occurred relatively recently. It is used in a wide number of disciplines including psychology, sociology, economics and anywhere else hierarchical data may occur (Garson, 2013, p.4) (Woltman, H., Feldstain, A., MacKay, J. C., & Rocchi, M. 2012). However it is beneficial to have high number of subjects as well as higher level groups in order to have sufficient power. Moreover it is important that there are no unobserved variables that could be confounding the results or at least have a Hausman test favorable for

HLM (Cook, "Fixed Effects vs Multilevel Models by William Cook", 2014). It will be valuable for statisticians and researchers to make use of this tool when appropriate over the long term as the person could be associated with fewer retracted papers over their career but I do not want you just to take the words of my sources and my own subjective assertions. The next section gives the results of a Monte Carlo simulation that may be useful to the reader in determining how concerned to be about multilevel data.

Part 2: More Evidence of the hazards of multilevel data by Monte Carlo Simulation

Objective

There is a table published in a 1987 edition of the American Statistician that gives the actual type I error for one-way ANOVA with an assumed alpha of 0.05 used on hierarchical data of varying numbers of groups, number of subjects per group and ICCs with all the rates having been calculated by an advanced theoretical method (Scariano & Davenport, 1987, p. 125). Please see appendix 9 for the actual table. It showed how even a small ICC can result in a high rate of type I error under the right conditions. It soon became clear that trying to replicate those results empirically would be a good objective in order to verify the reality of these findings for the many who do not have the time to learn the advanced methods used in the original paper. After numerous false starts, a feasible approach was found to try and approximate the table's findings by means of computer simulation, but in our case using a one sample t-test in place of a one-way ANOVA.

Method

The statistical software R was used as well as code from the internet that could produce hierarchical data. (Smart, 2013) We used a two level model in which the mean group effect (class effect) and subject effect (student effect) were zero and hence the overall mean would be zero. See appendix 1 for the model. Although previous versions necessitated cutting and pasting the program repeatedly albeit with a variable that would count each one, with Dr. Wolff's ingenuity the program became an ingenious looping algorithm. Please see appendix 8 for the actual code. It was a program that could randomly generate multilevel data of the original table's specifications and with a mean of zero a specific number of times and after each time performing a one sample t-test with a null

hypothesis of zero. The results of the tests were stored in a vector and then following the loop a few lines of code counted the number of tests with p value's less than or equal to 0.05 and divides that number rejected by the number of times run. Since we know that the true mean is zero and the t-tests' null hypothesizes where set to zero, this rate of rejection is approximate to the true type I error rate given a large enough number of t-tests are performed. The error rates were rounded to the nearest hundredth so that the table would be easier to read. The name of the overall technique that this program uses is called a Monte Carlo simulation.

In order to improve accuracy of the error rate, the program was changed from running 50,000 t-tests to 100,000 iterations per every error rate determination. Using the original table as a template, I made adjustments to the code for each run. This was to make sure that the group number and amount of group members as well as the value of the group's variance (in order to achieve the proper ICC) was correct for each corresponding table value. This process was continued until all 144 error rates were accounted for after a grant total of 14.4 million t-tests having been performed.

Results

The Table that this process yielded clearly shows how even a moderate ICC can result in a drastic increase actual type I error rate. See appendix 10 for the table that was made. For example if the null is true, and the assumed alpha is 0.05 as is typical and there are two groups of 30 members each hidden in the data with an ICC of a mere 0.1 then the true rate of type I error is over 6 times what you are expecting for your one sample t-test according to the table. Moreover despite the rounding, some tantalizing patterns are suggested from the data that may warrant further investigation in some instances. Not surprising with all other things being equal, as

the ICC increases, so does the actual rate of type I error. Also, with all things being equal provided ICC is not zero, as the number of subjects per group increases, the actual error rate does as well. The final more subtle and hence more tentative pattern that is discernable from my interpretations of the table is an interaction. For a given amount of subjects per group as the ICC increases and the number of groups increase, rate of type I error seems to decrease.

Discussion

Now it is time to bring some interesting points for discussion regarding my research. The last pattern is interesting as in the original table that uses ANOVA and is theoretical; with increasing number of groups, there is an increase in the error rate, all things being equal and assuming nonzero ICC. Certainly the original table's type I errors increase faster and to a greater extent in many places. Still both tables are able to show the same general idea albeit for two statistical methods. It is that for multilevel data, any moderate ICC can result in an increase in the true type I error when traditional techniques are employed, be they one-way ANOVA or a one sample t-test. This work has been exciting regardless of whether or not this t-test error rate table is original research or not. If someone has accomplished this task before, it is encouraging that a comparison can be made to assess the robustness of their results as well as my own; moreover, if there is no one else who has done this work, then it may serve as a stepping stone for others to build upon. Ideas of how one might go about this are expounded in the next section. Regardless, it is also important to mention that fixed effects models also remain a valuable way to handle hierarchical data albeit with a loss of generalizability that can be had with a multilevel level linear model.

Ideas for Future Research

The biggest disappointment of this research was not having been able to use one-way ANOVA with R to try and replicate the original table by means of simulation and thus spread some light on the validity of the table's theoretical underpinnings in a way accessible to the many math students who have not yet received their PHDS. It is also interesting to ponder whether there is some theoretical basis for calculating the true type I error for using a one sample t-test on hierarchical data. In other words, would there be some theoretical way to calculate the true error rate of one sample t-tests on hierarchical data? As that resulting table would be the one that be validated or refuted by this Monte Carlo simulation. It was also saddening not to having actually used a Hierarchical linear model. It would be interesting to redo this research with ANOVA but also include in the loop a Multilevel Linear Model as well as a fixed effects model and thus produce three tables and comparing the three techniques in handling the same randomly created data. That would be really exciting and was one of those paths abandoned in trying to accomplish this research.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I hope this paper has been able to inform the reader about the potential challenges of Hierarchical data and how multilevel modeling can be a useful tool to deal with it. Moreover, it is my hope the Monte Carlo Simulation research will either provide father validity for established research or to provide a stepping stone for others research in the future. Certainly it is clear from the simulation that multilevel data can have a great impact on the true type I error rate with even moderately sized ICC under the right

conditions. HLM is a serviceable way to reduce type I error as well as fixed effects models, but the reader should be aware of the strengths and weaknesses of both techniques and be willing to explore both possibilities in their research.

Acknowledgement

I would like to send my upmost gratitude to the incredible efforts of My professor Edward Wolff without his contributions in R coding and his insistence to just stick with a t-test in place of ANOVA, this project would not of been accomplished and I look forward to hearing about the work that others are able to contribute in the future. It is possible I might continue on with work myself depending on how busy I am. Also your ideas of Hierarchical data as being clustered and your visual interpretation of the ICC are brilliant.

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Appendix 1 simulation model

The image shows a screenshot of a PDF reader application window titled "newer quiz - Nuance PDF Reader 6.0". The window contains a single page with the following text:

$$y_{ij} = \mu + \mu_i + e_{ij}$$

where $\mu_i \propto N(0, \sigma_{class})$
 $e_{ij} \propto N(0, \sigma_{student})$

The window's interface includes a menu bar (File, Edit, View, Document, Comments, Forms, Tools, Window, Help), a toolbar with various icons (Convert PDF, E-mail, Search, Find, Select Text, Navigation Panels, Previous File, Next File), and a status bar at the bottom showing "8.50 x 11.00 in", "1 of 1", "131%", and the system clock "7:52 PM 12/14/2014". The Windows taskbar is visible at the bottom of the screen.

Appendix 2 example of level one equation for a given outcome value in a multilevel model

The image shows a screenshot of a Windows desktop with a PDF reader window open. The window title is "level 1 eq - Nuance PDF Reader 6.0". The menu bar includes "File", "Edit", "View", "Document", "Comments", "Forms", "Tools", "Window", and "Help". The toolbar contains icons for "Convert PDF", "E-mail", "Search", "Find", "Select Text", "Navigation Panels", "Previous File", and "Next File". A green banner at the top right of the toolbar says "Click [HERE](#) to learn more". The main content area of the PDF reader displays the following equation:

$$y_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}X_{ij} + \tau_{ij}$$

At the bottom of the PDF reader window, the page size is indicated as "8.50 x 11.00 in", the page number is "1 of 1", and the zoom level is "131%". The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows icons for Internet Explorer, Google Chrome, File Explorer, Skype, Spotify, Microsoft Word, and a calculator. The system tray in the bottom right corner shows the time "5:14 PM" and the date "12/14/2014".

Appendix 3 level 2 equations for a given subject in a multilevel model

Appendix 4
Scatter plot of multilevel data by Professor Edward Wolff

newer quiz - Nuance PDF Reader 6.0

File Edit View Document Comments Forms Tools Window Help

using PDF Converter Pro 7

Convert PDF E-mail Search Find Select Text Navigation Panels Previous File Next File

$$ICC = \frac{\sigma_{class}^2}{\sigma_{class}^2 + \sigma_{student}^2}$$

8.50 x 11.00 in

1 of 1 131%

8:05 PM 12/11/2014

Appendix 6

(Figure 1)

(Figure 2)

Appendix 7

Made up data

1 100
2 105
3 109
4 80
5 85
6 87
7 60
8 66
9 72

Appendix 8 R code developed by Professor Wolf from (Smart, 2013)

```
# Formula for class effect std deviation for a given ICC is

# ICC = squareroot((9*ICC/(1-ICC)) assuming student variance is 9

nclass = 5
nstud = 3

class.effect.std.dev = 0

student.effect.std.dev=3

class.effect = rnorm(nclass)*class.effect.std.dev

student.effect = rnorm(nstud*nclass)*student.effect.std.dev

data.set = data.frame(class.id = rep(1:nclass, each=nstud),
                      class.effect = rep(class.effect, each=nstud),
                      student.id = 1:(nstud*nclass),
                      student.effect = student.effect)

data.set$outcomes = data.set$class.effect + data.set$student.effect

Dotest<-t.test(data.set$outcomes,mu=0)

Ourpvalue <- Dotest$p.value

#now loop 99999 times

for (i in 1:99999) {
```

```
class.effect = rnorm(nclass)*class.effect.std.dev
student.effect = rnorm(nstud*nclass)*student.effect.std.dev

data.set = data.frame(class.id = rep(1:nclass, each=nstud),
                      class.effect = rep(class.effect, each=nstud),
                      student.id = 1:(nstud*nclass),
                      student.effect = student.effect)

data.set$outcomes = data.set$class.effect + data.set$student.effect

Dotest<-t.test(data.set$outcomes,mu=0)

Ourpvalue <- c(Ourpvalue, Dotest$p.value)
}

#Ourpvalue

#Ourpvalue<=.05

Nbr.reject=sum(Ourpvalue<=.05)

ErrorRate=Nbr.reject/100000
```

ErrorRate

```
ICC <- (class.effect.std.dev^2)/( class.effect.std.dev^2+ student.effect.std.dev^2)
```

ICC

Appendix 9 original table from (Stephen, 1987)

Untitled Prezi
True Lies - Nostalgia
Capstone - Google S
Computer Stock Pho
Inbox (6,677) - floeb
ezproxy.arcadia.edu

ezproxy.arcadia.edu:2079/stable/pdfplus/2684223.pdf?acceptTC=true&jpdConfirm=true
★

Apps
Imported From ...
ACS Get Experi...
Scholarship Ap...
Cappex.com - C...
Calculus III Vide...
AIP The American I...
ARIZONA JACK...
Netflix

test (2) at level α with the usual statistic $F = F_{12}(1, 1)$, believing the data to be iid when, in fact, V_1 is the true covariance matrix for the model. Let us compute the true probability of committing a Type I error for the decision rule in (6). In this case the likelihood ratio test statistic is actually $F_{12}(c_1 = 1 + (n-1)\rho, c_2 = 1 - \rho) = (c_2/c_1)F$, not F alone, and

as $n \rightarrow \infty$ or $\rho \rightarrow 1$ the true size of the usual test approaches 1, irrespective of the number of treatments being compared. Error covariance matrices of the type V_1 force the usual test to be too liberal at times, and increasing the sample size only worsens this problem. From a frequentist viewpoint, the usual statistic, F , which is not a true F variate in this context, rejects H_0 more times than necessary, not because

Table 2. True Type I Error Probabilities for the Test of Equality Among m Means for Case 1

m	n	ρ								
		.00	.01	.10	.30	.50	.70	.90	.99	
2	3	.0500	.0522	.0740	.1402	.2374	.3819	.6275	.7339	.8800
	10	.0500	.0606	.1654	.3729	.5344	.6752	.8282	.8809	.9475
	30	.0500	.0848	.3402	.5928	.7205	.8131	.9036	.9335	.9708
	100	.0500	.1658	.5716	.7662	.8446	.8976	.9477	.9640	.9842
3	3	.0500	.0529	.0837	.1866	.3430	.5585	.8367	.9163	.9829
	10	.0500	.0641	.2227	.5379	.7397	.8718	.9639	.9826	.9966
	30	.0500	.0985	.4917	.7999	.9049	.9573	.9886	.9946	.9990
	100	.0500	.2236	.7791	.9333	.9705	.9872	.9966	.9984	.9997
5	3	.0500	.0540	.0997	.2684	.5149	.7808	.9704	.9923	.9997
	10	.0500	.0692	.3151	.7446	.9175	.9798	.9984	.9996	1.0000
	30	.0500	.1192	.6908	.9506	.9888	.9977	.9998	1.0000	1.0000
	100	.0500	.3147	.9397	.9945	.9989	.9998	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
10	3	.0500	.0560	.1323	.4396	.7837	.9664	.9997	1.0000	1.0000
	10	.0500	.0783	.4945	.9439	.9957	.9998	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	30	.0500	.1594	.9119	.9986	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	100	.0500	.4892	.9978	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000

NOTE: The nominal level is $\alpha = .05$.

The American Statistician, May 1987, Vol. 41, No. 2 125

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significant differences actually exist among the treatments, but because the observations under the respective treatments are positively equicorrelated and this correlation inflates the true Type I error probability via the ratio $(1-\rho)/(1+\rho)$

Pr[Type II error]
 $= \Pr[F < F^*(m-1, N-m)]$
 $= \Pr[c_2 F/c_1 < c_2 F^*(m-1, N-m)/c_1]$

8:10 PM
12/11/2014

Appendix 10 new table developed by author

True type I Error Rates for One sample T-test on Multilevel Data

# of classes	# of Student				ICC						
M	2	n	0	0.01	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9	0.95	0.99
		3	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.12	0.18	0.26	0.37	0.41	0.44
		10	0.05	0.06	0.16	0.33	0.46	0.56	0.66	0.68	0.71
		30	0.05	0.08	0.33	0.56	0.67	0.74	0.8	0.82	0.83
	100	0.05	0.16	0.56	0.74	0.81	0.86	0.89	0.9	0.91	
	3	3	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.12	0.18	0.24	0.32	0.4	0.36
		10	0.05	0.06	0.15	0.33	0.44	0.53	0.6	0.62	0.64
		30	0.05	0.08	0.33	0.55	0.65	0.72	0.77	0.78	0.79
		100	0.05	0.16	0.56	0.74	0.8	0.84	0.87	0.88	0.88
	5	3	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.12	0.18	0.23	0.29	0.3	0.31
		10	0.05	0.06	0.16	0.32	0.43	0.51	0.57	0.58	0.59
		30	0.05	0.08	0.33	0.54	0.64	0.7	0.74	0.75	0.76
		100	0.05	0.17	0.56	0.73	0.8	0.83	0.86	0.86	0.87
	10	3	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.12	0.17	0.22	0.26	0.27	0.28
		10	0.05	0.06	0.15	0.31	0.41	0.49	0.55	0.55	0.56
		30	0.05	0.08	0.32	0.53	0.63	0.69	0.72	0.73	0.74
100		0.05	0.17	0.55	0.73	0.79	0.82	0.85	0.85	0.85	